

A checklist of bat species in northern Cambodia with new data from deciduous dipterocarp forests in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary

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Southeast Asia is experiencing one of the highest deforestation rates globally (Saravia *et al.*, 2018). Deciduous dipterocarp forests encompass approximately 156,000 km² within the region, mostly in Myanmar (79,000 km²), Thailand (37,000 km²) and Cambodia (23,000 km²), with remnant areas in Laos and Vietnam (Wohlfart *et al.*, 2014). These forests are characterized by open canopies and extensive grasslands which resemble African savannahs (Schwartz *et al.*, 2025) and experience a dry season from December to April and a wet season from May to October–November (Miles *et al.*, 2006; Pennington *et al.*, 2009). In Cambodia, deciduous dipterocarp forests mainly occur in the northern and eastern parts of the country and isolated waterholes within the forests provide important resources during the dry season for many endangered species including Asian elephants and giant ibises (Wohlfart *et al.*, 2014; Pin *et al.*, 2018; Legrand *et al.*, 2024). These waterholes (*trapeang* in Khmer) are threatened by human use, land conversion and potentially succession (due to the decline of large herbivores

which may have historically maintained waterholes via wallowing and trampling) (Neef, 2016; Eames *et al.*, 2018; Mamalis *et al.*, 2024). For example, research suggests ≈40% of waterholes in the Kulen Promtep and Chhaeb-Preah Roka wildlife sanctuaries in northern Cambodia were lost between 2011 and 2017 (Harrison & Mao, 2017).

Like other mammals, bats depend on water (Salvarina, 2016) and the importance of this escalates during reproductive periods (Webb *et al.*, 1995). The annual birth peak for insectivorous bats in Cambodia coincides with periods of water scarcity (March–April, the end of the dry season in Cambodia) (Lim *et al.*, 2018; Cappelle *et al.*, 2021) and because the importance of isolated water features in provisioning bats in water-stressed environments elsewhere is well documented (Lisón & Calvo, 2014; Korine *et al.*, 2015; Arzi *et al.*, 2023), the same can be reasonably assumed for waterholes and bats in deciduous dipterocarp forests. As with most other wild mammals, bats are also vulnerable to deforestation (Meyer *et al.*, 2015) and habitat loss is predicted to result in a 40% decline in the

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Fig. 1 Protected areas in north-central and northeast Cambodia. 1) Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary, 2) Chhaeb-Preah Roka Wildlife Sanctuary, 3) Phnom Tbaeng Natural Heritage Park, 4) Prey Lang Wildlife Sanctuary, 5) Siem Pang Wildlife Sanctuary, 6) Veun Sai-Siem Pang National Park, 7) Virachey National Park. Boundaries shown for Veun Sai-Siem Pang National Park and Virachey National Park predate the expansion of the parks in 2023 (RGC, 2023d, 2023e) as data on the present boundaries were not available at the time of writing

region's bat species by 2100 (Lane *et al.*, 2006). This poses a grave concern because bats can represent up to 50% of all mammal species in the tropical forests of Southeast Asia (Kingston *et al.*, 2006) and provide economically-significant and ecologically-important services including insect pest control, crop pollination and seed dispersal (Kunz *et al.*, 2011). Over 80 bat species have been recorded in Cambodia, although as many as 100 are expected to occur due to the presence of additional species in adjacent territories which may also occur in-country (Furey *et al.*, 2021).

While multiple efforts have been undertaken to restore waterholes in deciduous dipterocarp forests in Cambodia (e.g., Gray *et al.*, 2015; Legrand *et al.*, 2024; Auda & Sophim, 2025), these initiatives and associated monitoring efforts typically focus on large mammals and waterbirds despite their likely considerable importance for bat populations. We reviewed the literature and compiled unpublished data generated by research initiatives to create a checklist of bat species recorded between 2001 and 2023 in north-central and northeast Cambodia. We define these regions as including all areas within the Preah Vihear, Stung Treng and Ratanakiri provinces northwards of 13.5°N latitude (Fig. 1). We then supplement these data with the results of recent bat surveys in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary which build upon previous research in Preah Vihear Province (Walston & Bates, 2001; Matveev 2005; Hassanin & Tu, 2010; Furey & Csorba, 2011; Ith *et al.*, 2011; Chheang *et al.*, 2013; Furey, N. unpubl. data).

Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary (4,290 km²) includes parts of the Siem Reap and Oddar Meanchey provinces although most of the wildlife sanctuary is situated in Preah Vihear Province to the north of Phnom Tbaeng Natural Heritage Park (434 km²) (Fig. 1) (RGC, 2023a, 2023b). The sanctuary is contiguous with Chhaeb-Preah Roka Wildlife Sanctuary (3,476 km²) to the east (RGC, 2023c). While large areas of evergreen forest, semi-evergreen forest and rice cultivation exist, deciduous dipterocarp forests comprise the main forest type within the landscape and these extend eastwards across the Mekong River to the Veun Sai-Siem Pang (2,803 km²) and Siem Pang (1,323 km²) protected areas in the Stung Treng and Ratanakiri provinces (BICP, 2012; Clements *et al.*, 2013; MoE, 2017; RGC 2023d; McGrath *et al.*, 2024). Many hundreds of waterholes occur across the open forest landscape (BICP, 2012; Suzuki *et al.*, 2017), whereas in contrast, Virachey National Park (4,058 km²) mainly comprises closed evergreen and semi-evergreen forests which extend into the park from the Annamite Mountains in the northeastern tri-border area (BICP, 2012; RGC, 2023e; Roberts *et al.*, 2024).

To survey bats in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary, we deployed mist nets of various sizes mostly around waterholes within deciduous dipterocarp forests (Fig. 2). Nets were opened 30 minutes before sunset (1700–1800 hrs) and checked every ten minutes until they were closed at 2130 hrs. Standard measurements were taken of every bat captured and all bats were photographed and

Fig. 2 Waterhole during the dry season in deciduous dipterocarp forest

identified using Kruskop (2013) and Francis (2019) and unpublished keys developed by the first author. Live-trapping was avoided at the same location on consecutive nights to avoid trap familiarity and full moon periods were avoided where possible. Handling of bats followed Sikes *et al.* (2016) and all bats captured were released unharmed at their capture site the same evening. A total of 20 nights of live-trapping were undertaken between January and June 2025, 15 of which occurred during the dry season.

Our literature review indicates that approximately 59 bat species have been recorded in north-central and northeast Cambodia since 2001 (Table 1). These include several species which are very rarely recorded and poorly known such as *Hypsugo dolichodon*, *Murina walstoni* and *Otomops wroughtoni* (all Data Deficient [DD]) (IUCN, 2025). They also include species of conservation concern such as *Rousettus leschenaultii* and *Kerivoula picta* (Near-Threatened) and several taxa which have yet to be evaluated, namely *Rhinolophus chaseni*, *R. perniger*, *Cassidix yokdonensis*, *Tylonycteris malayana* and *T. fulvida*. While most of the latter are variably common and occur in several countries (Kruskop, 2013; Francis, 2019), *C. yokdonensis* is globally known only from three bats found at two localities, including one in Ratanakiri in 2018 (Ruedi *et al.*, 2017; Furey *et al.*, 2021). This recently-described genus and species appears to be genuinely rare and indicates the potential for discovery of other poorly

known bat species in the region. Further, while most of the species currently documented in northern Cambodia are presently categorized as Least Concern, population trends for almost half of these (27 of 59 spp.) are actually unknown.

We captured 148 bats representing at least 15 species during the surveys in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary (Table 1). Evening bats (Vespertilionidae) accounted for most captures with nine species (139 bats), followed by horseshoe bats (Rhinolophidae, 3 species), false vampire bats (Megadermatidae, 1 species) and fruit bats (Pteropodidae, 2 species). Aside from *Murina walstoni* (DD), all of these species are listed by IUCN (2025) as Least Concern, although population trends for six remain unknown. This is the first record of *M. walstoni* within the wildlife sanctuary (Fig. 3), although not unexpected as our capture site is only 220 km west of the type locality for the species in Veun Sai-Siem Pang (Csorba *et al.*, 2011). *Eptesicus pachyomus* was also recorded during our surveys (Fig. 3) and in Cambodia was previously only known from a single record in Ratanakiri Province, >250 km southeast of our capture locality (Furey *et al.*, 2021). In total, at least 11 bat species were recorded for the first time in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary during our survey, such that at least 15 bat species are now documented for the sanctuary. This equals one-fifth of the bat species presently known in Cambodia (Furey *et al.*, 2021).

Table 1 Checklist of bats recorded in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary and north-central and northeastern Cambodia since 2001. IUCN Status & Population Trend per IUCN (2025): LC=Least Concern, DD=Data Deficient (DD), NE=Not-evaluated, NT=Near Threatened, VU=Vulnerable. Data sources: a) Walston & Bates (2001), b) Matveev 2005, c) Hassanin & Tu (2010), d) Csorba *et al.* (2011), e) Furey & Csorba (2011), f) Ith *et al.* (2011), g) Furey *et al.* (2012), h) Chheang *et al.* (2013), i) Hayes *et al.* (2015), j) Furey *et al.* (2021), k) Furey (2023), l) Roberts *et al.* (2024), m) Guillebaud *et al.* (2025), n) Present study, o) Furey, N. unpubl. data. [] = Provisional record

#	Species	IUCN Status	Population Trend	Province			
				Preah Vihear		Stung Treng	Ratanakiri
				Kulen Promtep	Elsewhere		
I Pteropodidae							
1	<i>Megaerops niphanae</i>	LC	Stable		c e	c	c l
2	<i>Cynopterus sphinx</i>	LC	Increasing	c [n]	c e o	b c k m	c l
3	<i>Cynopterus brachyotis</i>	LC	Unknown	[n]		k	
-	<i>Cynopterus</i> sp.	-	-			m	
4	<i>Cynopterus horsfieldii</i>	LC	Unknown		h	h	
5	<i>Eonycteris spelaea</i>	LC	Decreasing			b c k m	c
6	<i>Rousettus amplexicaudatus</i>	LC	Unknown			b c m	c
7	<i>Rousettus leschenaultii</i>	NT	Decreasing			c	c
-	<i>Rousettus</i> sp.	-	-		e	m	
II Megadermatidae							
8	<i>Megaderma spasma</i>	LC	Stable	n o	e o	b c i k m	l
9	<i>Lyroderma sinense</i>	LC	Stable		c e	c i k m	c
III Hipposideridae							
10	<i>Hipposideros armiger</i>	LC	Stable		e	i k m	
11	<i>Hipposideros larvatus</i>	LC	Unknown		b	i k m	c l
12	<i>Hipposideros diadema</i>	LC	Decreasing		e f	f k	
13	<i>Hipposideros galeritus</i>	LC	Unknown		c e	i k m	c l
14	<i>Hipposideros cineraceus</i>	LC	Stable		e	b i k m	
15	<i>Hipposideros gentilis</i>	LC	Unknown		e	b c i k m	c l
IV Rhinolophidae							
16	<i>Rhinolophus marshalli</i>	LC	Unknown			i j k	
17	<i>Rhinolophus chaseni</i>	NE	-		e	c k	
18	<i>Rhinolophus malayanus</i>	LC	Stable	n o	c e o	i k m	l
19	<i>Rhinolophus acuminatus</i>	LC	Unknown		e	b k	c
20	<i>Rhinolophus pusillus</i>	LC	Stable	n	c o	c i k m	c l
21	<i>Rhinolophus affinis</i>	LC	Stable		c e	k	c l
22	<i>Rhinolophus shameli</i>	LC	Stable	n o	c e o	b c i k m	c l
23	<i>Rhinolophus microglobosus</i>	LC	Stable			i k m	l
24	<i>Rhinolophus perniger</i>	NE	-		c		c [l]
25	<i>Rhinolophus pearsonii</i>	LC	Unknown				l
26	<i>Rhinolophus stheno</i>	LC	Stable				c l
V Emballonuridae							
27	<i>Taphozous melanopogon</i>	LC	Stable		o	b i k m	
28	<i>Taphozous theobaldi</i>	LC	Unknown			b i k	

Table 1 Cont'd

#	Species	IUCN Status	Population Trend	Province			
				Preah Vihear		Stung Treng	Ratanakiri
				Kulen Promtep	Elsewhere		
VI Molossidae							
29	<i>Otomops wroughtoni</i>	DD	Unknown		a		
VII Vespertilionidae							
30	<i>Glischropus bucephalus</i>	LC	Unknown				c l
31	<i>Alionoctula javanica</i>	LC	Stable		g		
32	<i>Alionoctula coromandra</i>	LC	Unknown	n	[e]		
33	<i>Alionoctula tenuis</i>	LC	Stable			i	
34	<i>Alionoctula paterculus</i>	LC	Unknown	n	c [e] g	g	
-	<i>Alionoctula</i> spp.	-	-	n	e		
35	<i>Tylonycteris fulvida</i>	NE	-				l
36	<i>Tylonycteris malayana</i>	NE	-		e		c l
37	<i>Hypsugo cadornae</i>	LC	Unknown			g	
38	<i>Hypsugo dolichodon</i>	DD	Unknown			o	
39	<i>Hesperoptenus tickelli</i>	LC	Unknown	n	c e	b	
40	<i>Hesperoptenus blanfordi</i>	LC	Unknown		c e		
41	<i>Eptesicus pachyomus</i>	LC	Unknown	n			j
42	<i>Scotophilus kuhlii</i>	LC	Stable	n		b	
43	<i>Scotophilus heathii</i>	LC	Stable	n	e	b	
44	<i>Kerivoula hardwickii</i>	LC	Stable				c
45	<i>Kerivoula</i> cf. <i>depressa</i>	LC	Unknown		e		
46	<i>Kerivoula kachinensis</i>	LC	Stable				c
47	<i>Kerivoula titania</i>	LC	Unknown				c l
48	<i>Kerivoula papillosa</i>	LC	Stable				l
49	<i>Kerivoula picta</i>	NT	Decreasing		e f		
50	<i>Harpiocephalus harpia</i>	LC	Decreasing		e		l
51	<i>Murina walstoni</i>	DD	Unknown	n		d	
52	<i>Murina cyclotis</i>	LC	Unknown		e f	f	
53	<i>Eudiscopus denticulus</i>	LC	Unknown				l
54	<i>Myotis ater</i>	LC	Unknown	f [o]	e f	f	
55	<i>Myotis muricola</i>	LC	Stable		b		
56	<i>Myotis rosseti</i>	LC	Unknown	n			
57	<i>Myotis horsfieldii</i>	LC	Stable		f	f	
58	<i>Myotis hasseltii</i>	LC	Unknown			b	
-	<i>Myotis</i> sp.	-	-	n			
59	<i>Cassistrellus yokdonensis</i>	NE	-				j

Fig. 3 First records of A) *Murina walstoni* and B) *Eptesicus pachyomus* for Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary

That our brief survey could generate the first records of multiple bat species in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary illustrates how much remains to be learnt regarding bat populations within the sanctuary. The same is true of bats inhabiting understudied border areas nationwide in Cambodia (Furey *et al.*, 2021) and available data for Preah Vihear Province (Table 1) suggest future surveys could plausibly reveal as many as 23 additional bat species within Kulen Promtep. To this end, fieldwork should be undertaken within unsurveyed areas in the wildlife sanctuary, and particularly in evergreen and semi-evergreen forests. The same is true for the Chhaeb-Preah Roka and Phnom Tbaeng protected areas and while bats have been briefly surveyed in some sanctuaries (e.g., the Virachey & Veun Sai-Siem Pang national parks) in northern Cambodia, others in the Oddar Meanchay, Banteay Meanchay and Stung Treng provinces remain unsurveyed. Further, the fact that well over a dozen bat species inhabit adjacent areas of Laos and Vietnam, which likely occur in Cambodia but have yet to be recorded due to lack of survey effort (Furey *et al.*, 2021), also elevates the likelihood of future discoveries nationally.

Two-thirds of the bats recorded during our surveys in Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary were cryptic species (e.g., *Alionotula* [formerly *Pipistrellus*] spp. and small *Myotis* spp.) which could not be identified with certainty in the field (Table 1). While males of some *Alionotula* taxa (e.g., *A. paterculus*) are readily identifiable as their baculum (and thus penis) length and morphology is diagnostic (Furey *et al.*, 2012), field identification of females is extremely challenging (Kruskop, 2013; Francis, 2019). A similar difficulty applies to small

Myotis which is compounded by the reality that variations in the morphology of several new forms discovered in recent years (e.g., *M. annamiticus*, *M. annatessae*, *M. phanluongi*, *M. ancriola* & *M. hayesi*) have yet to be sufficiently described to permit reliable field identification. To address this, we will undertake a systematic review of specimens from Kulen Promtep Wildlife Sanctuary to confirm the correct name for each form present based on morphological (i.e. external, cranial, dental & bacula characters), acoustic and genetic data and determine reliable characters for their identification. Reference barcodes for verified species will be released via Genbank to assist future field identifications based on tissue samples.

Contemporary restoration efforts for waterholes in deciduous dipterocarp forest landscapes in Cambodia typically centre on ensuring continuous water availability during the dry season (Gray *et al.*, 2015; Legrand *et al.*, 2024). While studies elsewhere have shown that the use of isolated water features by bats is influenced by site-specific features (MacSwiney *et al.*, 2007; Razgour *et al.*, 2010; López-González *et al.*, 2016; Ancillotto *et al.*, 2019), their importance for bat populations in deciduous dipterocarp forests, though undoubtedly considerable, has yet to be quantified. The same is true of environmental factors that could result in differential waterhole use by bats and because such information could be instrumental in directing scarce management resources to better effect, we have begun acoustically monitoring bat activity at waterholes in northern Cambodia in an attempt to shed some light upon these matters. This effort will entail creation of a reference collection of echolocation calls produced by verified bat species and

employing this to develop a digital classifier capable of reliably identifying unseen bats registered by acoustic recorders. These resources will also be released without restriction to support future bat research and conservation efforts in Cambodia.

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